

Rationale for Code Commits Recruitment Survey

Study About the Rationale for Code Commits

Screening Questionnaire (3 min. estimated duration)

Modern software is modified in packaged changes called **code commits** in revision control systems. In many occasions, software developers need to **examine code commits** for various purposes. Some of the main motivations for examining code commits are:

- Debugging
- Reverse engineering requirements
- **Understanding rationale (Why is the code this way?)**
- ...

In this study, we want to understand developers' experiences when trying to understand the rationale for code commits.

During your software engineering activities, how often do you **inspect your own code commits to understand their rationale?**

- Few times per year
 - Multiple times per year
 - Multiple times per month
 - Multiple times per week
 - Multiple times per day
-

During your software engineering activities, how often do you **inspect other developers code commits to understand their rationale?**

- Few times per year
 - Multiple times per year
 - Multiple times per month
 - Multiple times per week
 - Multiple times per day
-

What is your gender?

- Male
 - Female
 - Decline to answer
 - Other
-

What is your age?

- 18-29
 - 30-39
 - 40-49
 - 50-59
 - 60+
-

How many years of experience do you have with software development?

Select all that apply, your software development experience is

- Personal
 - Professional (in a company)
 - Professional (open source)
-

How many years of experience do you have with version control systems (eg. Git, Github)?

Select all that apply, your experience with version control systems is

- Personal
 - Professional (in a company)
 - Professional (open source)
-

What version control systems have you used for software development?

- CVS
 - Git
 - Mercurial
 - Perforce
 - Subversion
 - Other (please specify) _____
-

The interview will be conducted in a conference room setting. Select your preference of interview location (select all that apply):

- VT campus
 - VT Corporate Research Center (CRC Knowledge Works II)
 - Remote interview (Skype)
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Please, select the most convenient times for you to have the **2 hours** interview session (select all that apply):

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
9:00 AM	<input type="checkbox"/>						
9:30 AM	<input type="checkbox"/>						
10:00 AM	<input type="checkbox"/>						
10:30 AM	<input type="checkbox"/>						
11:00 AM	<input type="checkbox"/>						
11:30 AM	<input type="checkbox"/>						
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5:00 PM	<input type="checkbox"/>						
5:30 PM	<input type="checkbox"/>						
6:00 PM	<input type="checkbox"/>						
6:30 PM	<input type="checkbox"/>						

What is your email address? Your email will be used only to contact you back for scheduling.
